

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/Preventive chemotherapies

Section

4.2 Preventive chemotherapies. In *WHO guidelines for malaria, 3 June 2022*.

Title

Malaria civil society organizations (CSOs) consultation for prevention using medicines: chemoprevention

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Context	
Date and hour	Thursday 29 October 2020 10AM-11AM GMT+1 and 05PM-06PM GMT+1
Place	ZOOM.US
Facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cecilia Senoo HFFG, Ghana • Marie Solange Ngoueko PHICC, Cameroon • Zeinabou Ide Impact Sante Afrique, Cameroon
Order of the day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria prevention using medicines: chemoprevention: General questions (In pregnancy and in children)
Context	
<p>WHO is starting a process to review its recommendations on the use of medicines to prevent malaria in people living in affected areas. As part of this process, WHO is keen to solicit perspectives from affected communities.</p> <p>Then, CS4ME (Civil Society for Malaria Elimination) led CSOs consultations in malaria issues for World Health organization. A questionnaire was elaborated on : general malaria issues, malarian & pregnancy and malaria & children. The questionnaire was shared through CS4ME WhatsApp platforms and by email. And also, 2 online consultations was conducted on October 29, 2020 (1 for French speaking and 1 for English speaking). The participants from francophone and anglophone Africa brought relevant responses to the questionnaire.</p>	
Course of the Activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria prevention using medicines: chemoprevention <p>Soliciting perspectives from communities & other stakeholders in countries with malaria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire for voluntary CSOs 	
<p>The Civil Society Organisations were both from Anglophone Africa and Francophone Africa. Their answers to these different questions are as follows;</p> <p>General Questions</p> <p>1. Who is most at risk of malaria in your setting?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 5 years • Pregnant women and their unborn child. • Young children, chronically ill individuals and pregnant women. • Pregnant women because lot of pregnant women die from malaria in Africa. <p>2. At what age are people at greatest risk of malaria in your setting?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 5 years. • Children under the age of 5 who still require guidance of covering themselves from mosquitoes. • Also, young adult men who are the working age group who are more exposed due to the nature of their jobs which are fishing so they camp out near river banks and the lakeside, Miners who are in swamping riversides doing gold panning. This age group is at especially at risk due to the fact that 	

men are supposedly supposed to be tough and if they fall ill they are supposed to be tough and “take it like men” so they might realise too late that the headache they thought was a simple headache was infect malaria and by the time they do seek medical assistance simple malaria would have developed into complicated malaria.

- In the middle area really landlocked the effects are very lamentable
- Rural and port environment
- Yes, but access to the service is a problem for the state of the health structure and access routes in the areas
- Self-medication is often used with the consequences of resistance cases.

3. What are the worst effects of malaria in your setting?

- Death, miscarriage, still birth sometime women go through complication during the labour/delivery.
- Loss of life, pregnant women miss carrying.

4. Are medicines used to prevent malaria in people at high risk of malaria in your setting?

- Yes
- Yes, medicines such as IPTp are administered to pregnant women after they pass their first trimester.
- There are no preventive medicines for malaria in the DRC, but in the endemic areas (Uvira, Kisangani, Fizi...) the community knows the signs and is treated. So, everything is based on treatment directly, I'm talking about traditional medicines.
- The artemether has become resistant due to self-medication
- Access to treatment
- Information on available services
- The adequate dose to be used
- Yes, they are already vulnerable targets, I think they are entitled

5. Can you share any experiences of malaria prevention using medicines?

- Yes, this experience is about the use of Sulphadoxine-Pyrimethamine (SP), before our intervention of implementation of malaria mostly the young girls who got themselves pregnant, women and pregnant women do not know the significant of taking SP during the pregnancy, but through our implementation of malaria program women and pregnant women including young girls are gradually understand the importance of taking SP every month. As at now the little work that we did some years back in terms of educating the pregnant women about the SP has proven positive, those who listen to the directives and take the SP for 5 times during the pregnant period are all delivered healthy baby child. I would say the SP drug which was meant for pregnant women is very GOOD FOR PREGNANCY, we shall continue to educate our women to take the drug if we would also continue implementing this program, we can achieve more than this.
- Most pregnant women did not realise the importance of taking IPTp seriously they would be given the first dose and due to the running water problems at health facilities they are at times instructed to take them at home, when they were given this chance, they would throw away these medicines and not take them. But after the 2020 malaria outbreak that had most in the community doubting if it was malaria to begin with or Covid-19, when they finally realised it was malaria the attitude towards malaria prevention changed. For those coming from areas which are malaria free they are given malaria medication to prevent them from contracting malaria when entering malaria zones.

6. What are the main challenges of using medicines to prevent malaria in your setting?

- Some of these challenges has to do with skin irritation, vomiting, weakness, sleepless night to some pregnant women when they take SP.
- Those individuals who normal take malaria preventative medication they in the long run become resistant to the medication when it's then used as a cure rather than a preventative measure.
- Some pregnant mothers only complete 2 dose of SPs and never continue again intensive engagement with pregnant mothers is needed at all times during their Antenatal days
- Dangers of terminating the life of the foetus, if taken at a delicate stage
- Weak knowledge about accessibility and free access to medicines.
- Popular imaginaries about free medication
- The main challenge is related to the low knowledge on the use of medicines
- The weight of social and cultural norms and the poor reception of at-risk populations by providers
- There are challenges between the availability of doses in very remote areas, information on products, advocacy for compliance with the 4 ANC's, etc.
- One of the biggest challenges is to combat self-medication
- To increase awareness of the need for care
- To facilitate, awareness raising needs to be strengthened

7. In your setting, do you think residents at increased risk of malaria should be given medicines to prevent malaria? Please explain your answer.

- Yes, the risk of malaria itself is deadly when considering some of the consequences it is irreversibly when it occurs. In the risk of malaria, the person suffers from permanent brain damage, physical disability, simultaneous abortion or miscarriage, still birth etc. all these are typical e.g. of severe type of malaria so malaria should be prevented in those areas.
- I believe that the use of medicines to prevent malaria would to a great extent make a huge difference especially if the medicine can be administered as a vaccine. This would help boost the immune system's defence against malaria meaning that there would have a fighting chance to resist the deadly disease.
- Yes, but because there is a need for accompanying measures, i.e. strengthening communication on available services, available structures and community implementation for community resilience against malaria.

8. What could be done to make it easier for people to use medicines to prevent malaria?

- The most importance thing to do is intensify the education awareness about malaria medicine / drug, am saying this because there are a lot of mixtures of herbs mix with other substance selling in the market, some churches, and prayer camps etc claiming to treat malaria. This is because people still don't believe the efficacy of the recommended medicine to treat malaria, if we embark on consistence strong advocacy program / campaign, people would understand it and this would be easier for them to use the malaria medicine to prevent malaria.
- The modification of the medicines into vaccines, and also the mandatory ANC bookings for all pregnant women this would ensure that no religion would override the intake of malaria medicines.
- Robust education to be given to the pregnant women to adhere to the prescribed malaria preventive drugs.
- Father's must be encouraged to support their pregnant mothers
- the current child friendly clinics at various hospitals must be sustain
- We also need more specialized child or children doctors
- Seasonal chimio prevention administration for children under 5
- Dealing with children mostly the only prevention we do is mosquitoes' net. Now for malaria drugs prevention will be good.

- Community Health Workers or Nurses must visit the residents at home more often to administer the drugs if the nursing mothers are refusing to turn up at the health facilities
- The ones I propose are CSO assistance and awareness raising documents

9. Have you any experience of malaria prevention using medicines in an emergency (e.g. disease epidemic, breakdown of the health system, civil unrest)? Can you share your experiences?

Additional information would be welcome from the respondents. In particular, is malaria very seasonal, e.g. does malaria occur each month of the year? If not, roughly how many months is the malaria season each year?

- Malaria in the Ghana is not a seasonal problem; we had malaria throughout the year in the country because of this AGRIDEF as local NGO is linking this question to how we can sustain the implementation of three diseases AFTER THE SUPPORT from global fund and WHO.
- Sustainability is the key when we talk of the programs and projects development and implementation, if a program is own by communities or beneficial or the grassroots the likelihood of sustainability is hundred percent (%) assured but if its own by regulators like how the three diseases was implemented so far in the previous years it has no sustainability assurance.
- We can ensure comprehensive sustainability if global fund descend directly to the grassroots or regions through the following means. Strategically, this is my suggestion Ghana is divided into 16 regions now with local NGOs across length and breadth in every corner in the country.
- Let the NGOs in every region form the regional base network. For example, western region has already formed the regional based network called Western Region Development Network of NGOs (WERENGO), we have our regional secretariat with executives in place, and the secretariat is currently working and managing 96 local NGOs across the region even though some are dormant and some are very active. These NGOs would integrate the three diseases when global fund strengthen them through the secretariat.
- Now plans have been made to reach companies, banks, institutions, firms etc next year to spell out the strategies put on board to support government to eliminate TB, HIV, Malaria, and also to fight climate change etc. in the region. The funds received from these companies, firms, banks etc every year would be use to continue the fight of the 3 diseases. The secretariat strategic plans are in line with government medium term development plan and SDGs.
- In the 2020 malaria outbreak in the 2 districts, the village health workers and the nursing stuff who usually assist in the curbing of such epidemics were afraid to go and test people who were falling ill let alone treat them this was due to the Covid-19 outbreak which was also roaming the world and the country the malaria symptoms and those for Covid-19 were too similar and the nurses who at the beginning did not have enough people, them risking their own health was not an option they were too keen to take.

IN PREGNANCY

1. Is malaria a problem in pregnancy? If so, in what way(s) is malaria a problem in pregnancy?

- Yes, malaria in pregnancy can cause death, miscarriage, still birth, deformity to unborn baby in the womb. It causes several damages to the pregnant woman.
- Malaria in pregnancy is an issue due to the weakened immune system of the pregnant mother, when they are given IPTp pregnant women hardly take malaria prevention seriously they are at times given malaria medicines but some don't take them.
- Yes, because it can affect the NN and the mother, the mortality and morbidity rate but also miscarriages. The financial cost of the treatment is high
- Yes, because if the pregnant woman has malaria, she may need more care on the vitamin side

2. What are the challenges for malaria prevention in pregnancy?

- Most of pregnant women generally don't attend the antenatal, because of other reaction of taken SP during pregnancy, these are; skin irritation, vomiting, body weakness, loss of appetite, sleepless night etc some other challenges also has to do with funds to attend antenatal clinic or hospital every month, some also in the connection with the behaviour of some nurses and the mode of treatment they exhibit before the client.
- Some religious groups strongly advocate for home deliveries and their women are restricted from antenatal care and this leads to this group not being able to take the necessary preventative drugs.
- I can still be biased to say yes to pregnant women because IPT is taken periodically and cannot create resistance, and also to the elderly, disabled people...who are vulnerable because of their movements to health centres.
- The first challenge during pregnancy is accentuated the sensation
- In view of the vulnerable status of pregnant women, their situation must be improved by giving them enough information on prevention
- To strengthen and raise awareness on access and availability of services
- Building community resilience in ANC
- Please scroll down the questionnaire page
- A great challenge is to involve spouses in the process
- I tell myself that the bp of mosquito nets is really not a problem, because in other countries they have but do not share where they are sold

3. Can you share any experiences of malaria prevention using medicines in pregnancy?

- Pregnant women refuse to take SP when prescribe to them.
- One of the pregnant women who later became an advocate of IPTp intake for pregnant women she herself was given the drug to prevent malaria and she like most women during that time would pretend to take the drug and she and other women would agree that the drug made them nauseated so it was not worth it to take it. She fell ill and had malaria and was given malaria treatment but unfortunately, she lost her baby so pregnancies that she had after the loss she had gone through she religiously took her preventative drug and encouraged other women to do so.

4. What could be done to make it easier to use medicines to prevent malaria in pregnancy? (e.g. change the number or timing of doses, or where the medicine is accessed, etc)

- Here where they can access the medicine is the challenges in my setting, some pregnant women trek / walk for at least 3 or more kilometres before they can reach health facility to take malaria medicine (SP). Due to that almost 70% of pregnant women in that season don't attend the antenatal clinic for the medicine.
- I will suggest that reaching pregnant women in their resident is key, a lot of local NGOs are around, and they can be trained to assist the health facilities to perform that function. Engage them in pregnant school is also a way to prevent malaria in pregnancy.
- If these medicines are administered at the health facility when the pregnant women go for antenatal care it would help but it would be most imp active if the village health workers would do follow up of pregnant women in their village and take the drugs to them because the other issue why pregnant women register their pregnancies late is due to the distances they have to travel to reach the nearest health facility.

5. What influences a woman's ability to get medicines to prevent malaria in pregnancy?

- In my case I always used a flip chart to educate them, there was a particular portion written Serious Risk of Malaria, the pregnant women got scared when they understand the content from that chapter. This chart has influenced the pregnant women a lot after we study the chart. Find the picture of the chart below.
 - Hearing the benefits of taking the medicines seeing other people who would give testimonials on how the drug benefited them and a reward of some sort to say for example the women who would have taken the complete required number of doses of IPTp would be given an incentive of some sort.
- 6. Is it equally important to prevent malaria in first and subsequent pregnancies?**
- This is very important to do that, because preventing malaria from the first time does not mean she cannot get the parasite again. Once the pregnant women always expose herself to the bite of mosquito, she has to prevent herself always not to get malaria.
 - It is equally important to prevent malaria in all pregnancies because the risks do not lower because one has had a child before.
- 7. Should women be given anti-malarial medicines (chemoprevention) to prevent malaria during pregnancy?**
- Yes.
 - Pregnant women who are amongst populations at risk of contracting malaria should be given anti-malarial medicines as long as they are safe and not harmful to the unborn baby.
 - When a woman is pregnant in her first trimester she receives her net and tpi

IN CHILDREN

- 1. Can you share any experiences of malaria prevention using medicines in children?**
- As a hypothesis child like to play and they are attracted to the comfort of tall grass and stagnant waters which are good breeding ground for mosquitoes and it is difficult to keep them from these areas so if they can be offered anti medicines the chances of them contracting malaria would be slim.
 - The distances that are being covered by villagers to access medicine are far too long for a 5 year old for instance to travel with their guardian far worse for those who would require to be carried once there are ill and the expected individual to carry this sick child is most likely to be their aged grandparent who has legs which are about to give, these are the very common scenarios in the communities we are working in. So, if village health workers are to be equipped with test kits and treatment packages at all times this would lessen the burden of the sick child and their caregiver.
- 2. What could be done to make it easier to use medicines to prevent malaria in children? (e.g. change the number or timing of doses, or where the medicine is accessed, etc)**
- Community health nurse system needs to strengthen so that they can reach the children and nursing mother. The use and education about LLIN should be intensify.
 - The distances that are being covered by villagers to access medicine are far too long for a 5 year old for instance to travel with their guardian far worse for those who would require to be carried once there are ill and the expected individual to carry this sick child is most likely to be their aged grandparent who has legs which are about to give, these are the very common scenarios in the communities we are working in. So if village health workers are to be equipped with test kits and treatment packages at all times this would lessen the burden of the sick child and their caregiver.
 - Create the listening centres where the CSO will play the role of distribution
 - Strengthen the capacity of the CSO in care and bring them closer together

3. Should children living in places with malaria transmission be given medicines to prevent malaria?

- Yes, and again the use of LLIN is key in such places.
- Children living in areas with malaria transmissions can be given preventive medicines, one can argue to say that they are less likely to contract the disease because of exposure theories. However, this argument I strongly go against it and share the view that if exposure theories truly guaranteed the necessary fighting chance which can be used to conclude that children should not be given preventive medicines then they would not be cases which reoccur and patients who fall ill and sick of malaria more than once in season.
- Children are the most vulnerable to malaria they must receive preventive treatment
- No for me
- Yes, because since we don't use medicines to prevent children from coming in with serious cases.
- Yes, prevention must be resumed for children under 5 years of age

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR VOLUNTARY CSOs

This questionnaire was given to voluntary Civil Society Organisations who responded to the different questions as follows;

- **Should women be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention during pregnancy?**
 - a) Phase 1: Should women of all gravidities be given sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) as malaria chemoprevention during pregnancy?
 - Yes. But Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine should only be used during pregnancy if the benefit outweighs the risk to the fetus, because pyrimethamine is a folate antagonist, folic acid supplementation should be given during pregnancy.
 - Pregnant women in the first trimester should be excluded from this intervention to prevent drug induced embryological abnormalities or birth defects. But pregnant women after 13months quickening can rather receive IPT. Not all pregnant women should be given SP as malaria chemoprevention for safety reasons.
 - No
 - b) Phase 2: Should women be given antimalarial drugs other than SP as malaria chemoprevention during pregnancy?
 - Yes, especially if the women are reacting to Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine; or if there is SP resistance.
 - For treatment of malaria, other drugs such as atemeter lumefatrine can be used in treating malaria in pregnant women. Currently, studies have shown the efficacy and safety of Sulphadoxine Pyrimethamine in pregnancy. It remains the safest malaria chemoprevention drug for pregnant women, so safety of mother and the child should supersede.
 - Yes

- ❖ **The GDG may decide to manage some of these additional considerations (and those of the other PICO questions) as specific sub-group analyses. More operational considerations may be flagged for consideration in implementation manuals or related documents.**

- **Should children living in settings with perennial malaria transmission be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention?**
 - a) Phase 1: Should infants living in settings with perennial malaria transmission be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention?
 - Yes
 - Yes. They are more vulnerable to malaria. Giving them malaria chemoprevention would be more beneficial.
 - Yes

 - b) Phase 2: Should children living in settings with perennial malaria transmission be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention?
 - Yes
 - Yes, definitely.
 - Yes

- **Should children living in settings with seasonal malaria transmission be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention?**
 - a) Is mass drug administration (MDA) a safe and effective approach to reduce the burden of malaria in moderate and high transmission settings?
 - Yes
 - Yes. Though there is a serious need for community involvement in the planning and implementation stages of it especially in developing countries. Mass Drug Administration could hypothetically act as creating community shield against malaria. If this could be studied repeatedly in malaria endemic communities, it could probably bring massive result.
 - No

 - b) During emergencies or periods of health service disruption, should people living in malaria-endemic settings be given anti-malarial medicines for chemoprevention?
 - Yes
 - Definitely. People are more vulnerable to malaria in times of crisis or emergencies and periods of health service disruptions, most especially, displaced people. Malaria chemoprevention should be given to such people as part of managing disaster. In fact, countries should include such an intervention as part of disaster management policies.
 - Yes

- **Should children hospitalized with malaria or severe anaemia in malaria-endemic settings be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention post-discharge?**
 - Yes
 - Yes, to prevent recurrence of malaria.
 - No

Malaria CSOs consultation for prevention using medicines: chemoprevention

- **In areas of moderate to high malaria transmission, should residents known to be at increased risk of clinical malaria, severe malaria, death, or other adverse effects of P falciparum infection, be given anti-malarial medicines as chemoprevention?**
 - Yes
 - Yes. This should rather be done through community approach for effectiveness.
 - No

N°	Online consultations CSOs participants
1	PHICC
2	Hope For Future Generation
3	ONG AWA
4	ASAPSU
5	APROSAM
6	AFEDEC
7	Organisation des Femmes pour l'Islam sans Frontière
8	Plateforme des ONGs et Associations de lutte contre le Paludisme en République du Congo
9	ONG AWA
10	Organisation Nigérienne des Educateurs Novateurs
11	APDSP (Approche Participative, Développement et Santé de Proximité)
12	APEE COTE D'IVOIRE
13	Association pour la Promotion et l'Intégration de Jeunesse du Centre Nord (APIJ-CN)
14	FENOS-CI
15	ONG ZONAL
16	One Health - Communication for development in Action
17	Association des Anciens Patients Tuberculeux du Bénin (ASSAP-TB/BENIN)
18	Association féminine vision positive (AFVIPO)
19	Community Engagement for Malaria Elimination in Zambia (CEMEZ)
20	Concern Health Education Project
21	Agriculture-Environmental and Infrastructure Development Foundation (AGRIDEF)
22	Human Service trust